

INTERACTIVE EFFECTS OF GOVERNMENT INTEGRITY AND PUBLIC SPENDING ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This paper investigates the individual and joint impacts of government integrity and public spending on economic growth in Nigeria, by using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) technique covering 1981 to 2021. It modelled the interactive effect of government integrity and fiscal spending relying on disaggregated form of the Keynesian framework. The results reveal that public expenditure has negative impact on growth in the short-run; and as such negates the Keynesian dictates. However, capital spending had significant positive impact on growth in the long-run. Surprisingly, the effect of the interaction between government integrity and public spending remained negative both in the short and long-run periods. This implies that government integrity substitutes or reduces the effect of public spending on economic growth in Nigeria within the study period. Thus, the paper recommends policies geared towards increasing and ensuring optimum implementation of capital spending on projects within the budget year. In addition, the legislature should increase their oversight functions focused on the preparation of appropriation bills, budget monitoring and implementation processes in order to enforce transparency and integrity of government officials involved at all stages of the budgeting process

Keywords: Public spending, Government integrity, Economic performance, ARDL, Keynesian theory

1 Introduction

Fiscal policy is associated with revenue generation and spending by the government targeted at amplifying levels of economic activities. According to Edeme and Nkaku

(2016), government expenditure can be either capital or recurrent in nature. Some sources of income generation by the government are taxes, grants and commodities' export utilized to ensure macroeconomic stability. Notably, macroeconomic stability can be derived through employment generation, price stability, balance of payments and sustainable economic growth (Uremadu, Orikara & Uremadu, 2019).

Most often, economic growth is the most crucial determinant and influencer of economic welfare; hence, growth determinants have been of great importance in both theoretical and applied studies in the past two decades (Sulaeman & Sukmana, 2023). Similarly, government spending-economic growth relations has been phenomenal among economists and policy-makers across the globe; especially with the recent coronavirus pandemic which has disrupted government revenue sources as well as simultaneously increased health and social protection expenditures in developed and developing economies (Nwokolo, Ogbuagu & Iwegbu, 2020).

In literature, there are basically two diverging theories on the link between government spending and economic growth, and they include Keynesian theory and Wagner's law. Following the dictates of Wagner's proposition, economic performance and fiscal spending possess a positive relationship, and the direction of causation moves from a rise in economic activity to an equivalent up-shoot in fiscal spending (d'Agostino, Dunne & Pieroni, 2016). In contrast, Keynesian theory posits that growth in fiscal spending often triggers a higher level of total demand, which in turn promotes growth (Bounsaythip & Inthakason, 2022). Thus, in view of the Keynesian theory, government has a specific role to play in achieving appreciable levels of economic growth across economies of the world. Despite the above contending issues, this study is abreast with the position that government expenditure in the Keynesian ideology tends to lay more credence on the effectiveness and contributions of capital spending towards achieving growth compared to the recurrent fiscal spending (Gushnibet & Tsenba, 2016; Uremadu et al., 2019).

Besides these factors driving economic growth in the theories above, government integrity plays a crucial role by strengthening public expenditure to exert multiplier effects. It evaluates the quality of institutional controls to manage the risk of corruption across government agencies, ministries and departments (Emmanuel, Usifoh & Adu, 2024; Muhammad et al., 2023). As observed in other developing economies in Africa and Asia, government integrity and institutional efficiency in Nigeria are at the lowest ebb (Shon & Cho, 2019; Qiongzhi & Chan, 2019). Often, this has triggered bogus wage bills, increased prices, exaggerated contract budgets and estimations; thereby, creating political uncertainties and economic backwardness (Abdullah & Habibullah, 2020). According to the Heritage Foundation (2022), the average index of government integrity in Nigeria between 1995 and 2019 was a meager 22.52 on a scale of 0-100, which is relatively poor.

The trend of Nigeria's fiscal recurrent expenditures has been up-surgingly since the inception of the democratic dispensation in 1999, reaching over 8 trillion naira in 2022. Also, capital spending follows a similar pattern and struck over 5 trillion naira in 2022. These upward trends in fiscal spending might be inflationary driven through exchange rate volatility, which has depreciated the naira over the years. Overall, recurrent and capital expenditure have continually shared about 70 percent and 30 percent, respectively, for over two decades (Ayeni, Saman & Sani, 2019). Comparatively, South Africa's average capital spending between 1980 and 2018 was approximately 47.5 percent; however, Nigeria recorded approximately 28.75 percent within the period (World Development Indicator, 2022).

The continual rising trend in government recurrent expenditures has generated varying degrees of arguments among social commentators, economic and political analysts. Following the current trend of public expenditure, the Nigerian budget gives dimming hope for economic growth and development (Edeme et al., 2018). This is because the over-bloated spending on servicing elected officials and other government representatives should have been channeled to infrastructural investments, which have a higher multiplier effect on the economy (Selamawit, 2018). Notably, challenges such as corruption, misappropriation, mismanagement and waste might call into questioning the level of government integrity in Nigeria. Drawing from these existing arguments, it is necessary to compare the contributions of capital and recurrent expenditures to economic performance (Iheanacho, 2016), and the joint impact of government integrity and public expenditure on economic growth, by employing the ARDL methodology on a Nigerian dataset in order to analyze the impacts of the explanatory variables in the short- and long-run periods, as well establish their linear relationship. Disaggregating the effects of government spending and determining the catalyst role of government integrity on economic growth are the main additions to existing knowledge. The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the empirical review; Section 3 lays down the Methods; Section 4 discusses the results, and Section 5 presents the conclusion and policy recommendations.

2. Empirical Literature

A study by Ogbuagu and Ekpenyong (2015), using the ARDL technique and the Toda-Yamamoto causality test, examined the effects of fiscal spending on output performance in Nigeria. The study reveals that capital and recurrent expenditures exert negative and positive effects on output growth, respectively, in the long-run. Also, the causality test confirms Wagner's law since it is uni-directional, emanating from growth to aggregate fiscal expenditures. The paper recommends policies focused on comprehensive implementation of capital expenditure as contained in the appropriation bill.

In addition, examining both short- and long-run relationships between fiscal expenditure and output growth in Nigeria, Iheanacho (2016) employed the error correction model (ECM) and Johansen cointegration. They found that recurrent spending exerts direct and inverse effects on output growth in the short- and long-run periods, respectively. It is based on this premise that the paper concluded by advocating for effective utilization of funds and monitoring of the budget implementation process. Furthermore, Uzoma-Nwosu (2018) examined the causal effect of fiscal expenditure on GDP performance in Nigeria, covering the 1970 to 2016 period. Findings from the paper reveal that the Granger causality result confirms bidirectional links between the variables under investigation (see Granger, 1969).

More so, Anowor and Nwanji (2018) relied on the error correction mechanism (ECM) and Granger causality techniques to re-examine the nexus between fiscal spending and growth performance in Nigeria and found an inverse relationship as well as unidirectional causality moving from GDP growth to public expenditures. The authors recommended increment in capital spending as well as improve monitoring of the budget implementation process. Further, Edeme et al. (2018) examined the validity of Wagner's law using the Granger causality technique on data between 1981 and 2015. The authors discovered bi-directional links between fiscal spending and economic performance, and concluded that growth enhancers such as economic, social and community services cannot be overemphasized.

Okolo, Edeme and Emmanuel (2018) investigated the effects of capital spending on infrastructure in Nigeria covering 1970 and 2017 using the ARDL technique. Here, the authors discovered that a positive relationship exists between recurrent expenditure and infrastructural development. Uremadu, Oriokara, and Uremadu (2019) dissected the impact of recurrent spending on GDP performance in Nigeria between 1998 and 2017 using the OLS method. The paper found that recurrent expenditure exerts a positive influence on economic performance. Ayeni et al. (2019) dissected the effects of government spending on economic growth in Nigeria, and discovered that capital spending exerts a positive and significant impact on economic growth.

Aigheyisi and Edore (2015) reviewed the link between government purchases, good governance, and GDP growth in Africa. Relying on the Keynesian model, they argued that public procurement and good governance are complementary; and could positively influence growth. The paper suggested robust procurement practices as a panacea to facilitate growth within the African continent. Baklouti and Boujelbene (2016) extended the neoclassical model by incorporating government size and quality, focused on examining the interactive effect of corruption and government size on economic performance in the MENA region. The paper revealed that the larger the public sector, the higher the corruption index, which thereby negatively influenced economic performance. Based on this premise,

they stressed the need to invest in capacity, which strengthens governance and enhances growth.

More significantly, Abdullah and Habibullah (2020), and Nawaz and Khawaja (2018) introduced institutional quality into the fiscal spending-growth relationship. The latter examined impact of fiscal policy on economic performance in 56 countries and discovered that fiscal policy exerted positive and negative effects on GDP growth in advanced and less developing economies. Al Qudah, Zouaoui and Aboelsoud (2020) dissected the links between corruption and economic growth using the ARDL technique in Tunisia from 1995 to 2014. The paper revealed that corruption has direct and indirect negative effects on gross domestic product (GDP) per capita and fiscal investment, respectively, in the long term. Thus, measures to reverse the corruption perception index are a pathway to improving growth.

On the part of Qiongzhi and Chan (2019), they utilized the data envelope analysis (DEA) model to examine differences in transportation effectiveness in the presence of varying degrees of regional government integrity across 3 Chinese provinces between 2006 and 2018. The paper confirmed that provinces with a low degree of government integrity recorded low infrastructural efficiency. Further, Shon and Cho (2019) examined the relationships between fiscal decentralization and corruption among government officials in US state and local government councils using historical and empirical literature. The authors found that more decentralized structures within the US foster corruption among government officials.

According to Transparency International (2019), corruption perception index (CPI), measures the level of corruption which is annually computed. This organization ranks about 180 nations on a scale of 0 to 100. In 2020, Nigeria was ranked 146 on the global corruption index, scoring approximately 32 percent on the scale, which justifies her classification as one of the globally most corrupt nation. There are four foundational steps in computing the CPI, including the collection of survey data, data rescaling, aggregating rescaled data, and testing the level of data certainty. It is based on these logical steps that Nigeria's professionals perceive the CPI as accurate; and as such approach it with "full trust".

In summary, the empirical literature shows that the closest to this paper were those of Nawaz and Khawaja (2018) and Abdullah et al. (2020). However, this paper models the government integrity index as highlighted in Qiongzhi and Chan (2019) and examines the joint effects of fiscal spending and government integrity on output growth by employing the ARDL technique. Thus, contributing to the existing literature.

3 Methodology

3.1 Theoretical Model

To investigate the disaggregated effects of public expenditures on economic performance, the paper built its empirical foundation on the Keynesian theory. This theory presupposes that public expenditures enhance aggregate demand within an

economy through the employment and income generation pathway. A study by Ogbuagu and Ekpenyong (2015) have adopted the Keynesian theory; however, we expand this model by adding government integrity as a control variable as well as the interaction between capital spending and government integrity index (Musa et al., 2022) as specified below:

$$EGR_t = f(CEX_t, REX_t, A_t) \quad (1)$$

Where EGR is economic growth, CEX and REX represent capital and recurrent expenditure and A include other control variables such as: household consumption, private investment, net export, interest rate, exchange rate and government integrity index. Notably, government integrity was added into the model because of the arguments that it improves the influence of fiscal spending on economic performance and efficiency in China (Qiongzhi & Chan, 2019). Thus, the Keynesian model is modified and re-specified in the linear functional model below:

$$EGR_t = f(CEX_t, REX_t, CON_t, INV_t, NX_t, EXCH_t, INT_t, GOINT_t) \quad (2)$$

Where EGR = Economic growth, CEX = Capital expenditure, REX = Recurrent expenditure, INV = Private Investment, NX = Net export, EXCH = Exchange rate, INT = Interest rate, GOINT = Government integrity

Re-specifying into mathematical form of the model becomes:

$$EGR_t = \delta_0 + \delta_1 CEX_t + \delta_2 REX_t + \delta_3 CON_t + \delta_4 INV_t + \delta_5 NX_t + \delta_6 EXCH_t + \delta_7 INT_t + \delta_8 GOINT_t \quad (3)$$

Where EGR = Economic growth, CEX = Capital expenditure, REX = Recurrent expenditure, INV = Private Investment, NX = Net export, EXCH = Exchange rate, INT = Interest rate, GOINT = Government integrity, δ_0 = Intercept, $\delta_1 - \delta_8$ = Coefficients of the variables.

3.2 Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Technique

ARDL is a dynamic model which captures the impact of explanatory variable X on Y (explained variable) over time. This present study relies on autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model as the estimation technique because it determines both immediate and remote links between the variables. Further, unit roots confirming the combined integration of zero and one suggests the ARDL methodology. Thus, following Pesaran, Shin and Smith (2001), the fiscal spending-economic growth relation is expressed in ARDL equation form as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta EGR_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_1 \Delta EGR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_2 \Delta CEX_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_3 \Delta REX_{t-1} \\
 & + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_4 \Delta CON_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_5 \Delta INV_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_6 \Delta NX_{t-1} \\
 & + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_7 \Delta EXCH_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_8 \Delta INT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_9 \Delta GOINT_{t-1} \\
 & + \beta_1 \ln EGR_{t-1} + \beta_2 \ln CEX_{t-1} + \beta_3 \ln REX_{t-1} + \beta_4 \ln CON_{t-1} \\
 & + \beta_5 \ln INV_{t-1} + \beta_6 \ln EXCH_{t-1} + \beta_7 \ln INT_{t-1} + \beta_8 \ln NX_{t-1} \\
 & + \beta_9 \ln GOINT_{t-1} \\
 & + ECM(-1) + \varepsilon_t
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Where Δ connotes first difference, EGR is economic growth, CEX is capital expenditure as a ratio of GDP, REX is recurrent expenditure, CON is household consumption, INV is private investment, NX and EXCH are net exports, and exchange rate respectively, while INF, INT and GOINT are Inflation rate, interest rate and government integrity. p is the lag length, α and β are the parameters and ε_t is the error term.

Note: The first part of the equation 4 with the summation sign is the short-run equation, while the remaining part is the long-run equation.

Since the study interacted government expenditure and government integrity (see Sum, 2013), the resultant ARDL equation becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta EGR_t & = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_1 \Delta EGR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_2 \Delta CEX_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_3 \Delta REX_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_4 \Delta CON_{t-1} \\
 & + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_5 \Delta INV_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_6 \Delta NX_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_7 \Delta EXCH_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_8 \Delta INT_{t-1} \\
 & + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_9 \Delta GOINT_{t-1} \\
 & + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_{10} CEX * GOINT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \alpha_{11} REX * GOINT_{t-1} + \beta_1 \ln EGR_{t-1} \\
 & + \beta_2 \ln CEX_{t-1} + \beta_3 \ln REX_{t-1} + \beta_4 \ln CON_{t-1} + \beta_5 \ln INV_{t-1} + \beta_6 \ln EXCH_{t-1} \\
 & + \beta_7 \ln INT_{t-1} + \beta_8 \ln NX_{t-1} + \beta_9 \ln CEX * GOINT_{t-1} + \beta_{10} \ln REX * GOINT_{t-1} \\
 & + \beta_{11} \ln GOINT_{t-1} \\
 & + \varepsilon_t
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Where β_9 and β_{10} are the coefficients of the interactive effects, which differentiates equation 4 and 5. Also, it is expected a-priori that all the explanatory variables

except interest rate would have positive effects on economic growth. Hence, the econometric estimate is explained below as:

$$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, \alpha_5, \alpha_6, \alpha_7, \alpha_9, > 0; \alpha_8 < 0; \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_8, \beta_9, \beta_{10}, \beta_{11} > 0; \beta_7 < 0$$

This current paper adopted the ARDL method because of the time series properties as well as the ability of the ARDL technique to analyse impacts of the explanatory variables in the short-and long-run periods. The time series data spans from 1981 through 2021, hence, covers a period of 41 years. These time series data are sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2022), World Bank Development Indicators (WDI) 2022 and the Heritage Foundation 2022 databases.

4. Results

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

This sub-section strives to provide statistical description of variables within the model as well as economic interpretations based on their individual statistical characteristics within the context of the discourse (Table 1). The average economic growth rate stood at 3.21% between 1980 and 2018 which is the study periods. Further, it can be asserted that the median stood at 4.23% which is higher than the mean value by approximately 1.01%. The highest and lowest values were pegged at 15.33% and -13.13% respectively. The series on public capital expenditure behaved differently from the former (GDP growth series), since the mean value of capital expenditure (376.46 billion naira) is greater than the median value (269.65 billion naira) by approximately 107.80 billion naira. The maximum and minimum values are 1152.8 billion and 4.1 billion naira respectively. Comparing these figures with the former, it cannot be argued that government expenditures over time have been tilted towards recurrent spending (Ekanayake & Thaver, 2021; Hieu & Mai, 2022).

Table 1: Statistical Description of Variables

	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Observations
GDPGR	3.2085	4.230	15.33	-13.13	41
CEX	376.46	269.65	1152.8	4.10	41
REX	1150.27	449.66	4290.0	4.75	41
CON	1089.61	933.79	1667.50	657.39	41
INV	36.685	36.58	89.386	4.170	41
NX	5.12E+09	2.83E+09	2.44E+10	-2.36E+10	41
EXCH	82.665	92.34	305.79	0.618	41
INTR	0.038	3.024	18.18	-65.86	41
GOINT	27.93	27	50	7	41

Source: Authors' computation (2023)

4.2 Test of Stationarity

This section presents the Phillip-Perron and Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) tests. These tests are pre-diagnostics to determine appropriate estimation method to employ (Table 2).

Table 2: Phillip-Perron and Augmented-Dickey Fuller Unit Roots Tests

Variables	Phillip-Perron Test		Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test	
	At Level (I(0))	First Diff (I(1))	At Level (I(0))	First Diff (I(1))
GDPGR	-1.136 (0.7005)	-4.385* (0.0003)	-3.142** (0.032)	-10.357* (0.000)
CEX	-1.035 (0.740)	-5.639* (0.0000)	-1.488 (0.529)	-7.157* (0.000)
REX	-1.834 (0.3639)	-4.785* (0.0001)	-2.212 (0.205)	-5.908* (0.000)
CON	-1.431 (0.5673)	-3.459* (0.0091)	-1.271 (0.634)	-2.96** (0.04)
INV	-3.535* (0.0071)	-7.170* (0.0000)	-3.583* (0.000)	-6.780* (0.000)
NX	-2.223 (0.1979)	-8.111* (0.0000)	-2.378 (0.154)	-7.760* (0.000)
EXCH	3.359 (1.000)	-4.156** (0.002)	2.9540 (1.000)	-4.2416* (0.0017)
INTR	-4.21 (0.002)	-12.614* (0.000)	-2.310 (0.1.735)	-5.512* (0.000)
GOINT	-1.857 (0.349)	-4.069 (0.003)	-0.2328 (0.657)	-6.981 (0.000)

Note: *, ** and *** indicate 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance respectively. P-values are in parenthesis.

Source: Authors' compilation (2023)

From the unit roots test in Table 2, it is observed that variables such as GDP growth rate, interest rate, recurrent expenditures and exchange rate are stationary at level, and are significant at 1% and 5% levels. On the other hand, series such as capital expenditure, private consumption, exchange rate, government integrity, and net export were integrated of order one (first difference) at 1% and 5% significance.

4.3 Cointegration Analysis

Thus, it is pertinent to examine whether or not the series reverse back their mean in the long-run or otherwise. This is ascertained using the bounds testing approach presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Bounds Testing Cointegration

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif	I (0)	I (0)
F-Statistic	7.299	10%	3.03	4.06
K	4	5%	3.47	4.57
		1%	4.4	5.72

Source: Author’s computation (2023)

The co-integration analysis as presented in Table 3 shows that the probability of the F-statistic (5.87) is 0.0006. Based on this observation, it can be concluded that the mean of the series reverses back to their steady-state after a short-term distortion. Thus, the variables co-integrate in the long run. This finding is a litmus test and sufficient condition for the selection of the ARDL methodology from the basket of options.

VAR Lag Length Selection

Despite this clarifications, it is crucial to test for lag-length using the variance autoregressive (VAR) lag selection criteria test (Table 4).

Table 4: VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-652.437	NA	1.11e+13	38.555	38.690	38.601
1	-551.557	178.024*	5.02e+10*	33.150*	33.689*	33.334*
2	-547.052	7.155	6.64e+10	33.415	34.358	33.736
3	-540.227	9.635	7.82e+10	33.543	34.890	34.002

Note: * Represents that the lag 1 is significant

Source: Authors’ computation, 2023

This table presents the lag lengths, ranging from 0 to 3. The result reveals that only lag length one is significant based on Akaike information criterion, likelihood ratios, Hannan-Quinn criterion and Schwartz criterion. The next is the presentation and interpretation of the short and long-run regression results (Tables 5a and 5b).

4.3 Short-run Relationship of the Variables

The Table 5 shows the short-run impact of explanatory variables on the dependent variable in the short-run. The result shows that capital expenditure has a negative impact on economic growth, which is in tandem with the works of Ogbuagu and Ekpenyong (2015) and Emmanuel et al. (2024). Indicating that a one billion-naira increase in capital expenditure will reduce economic growth by 0.013%, holding other variables constant. Similarly, the results show a negative relationship between

recurrent expenditure and economic growth. This implies that a one billion-naira increase in recurrent expenditure would cause GDP per capita growth rate to fall by 0.002%. Although these results do not support the *a priori* expectations as captured in the Keynesian theory, it supports the works of Modebe, Okafor, Onwumere and Imo (2012) and Muhammad et al. (2023). Subsequently, the impact of government integrity on economic growth is positive. This is evident on the premise that a 1-unit increase in the government integrity index would increase economic growth by 0.004%, which supports *a priori* expectations.

In addition, the impact of the interaction of recurrent expenditure and government integrity on economic growth is negative. Although it presents room for argument that the relation between government integrity and recurrent expenditure is substitute in nature, the finding does not support *a priori* expectations (Muhammad et al., 2023). The impact of the lagged value of the error term is negative, and supports the proposition that short-run disequilibrium occurs. In the same vein, the long run regression result shows that the impact of capital expenditure on economic growth is positive. This is because as capital expenditure increases by one billion naira, the rate of economic growth increases by 0.008 percent, holding other variables constant. This result supports the a-priori expectation since the Keynesian theory postulates that economic growth can only be achieved through an increase in government expenditure (Gushibet & Tsenba, 2016; Musgrave & Musgrave, 1989). Contrary to the above, the table shows that the impact of recurrent expenditure on growth maintained negative on the growth rate of GDP per capita income. This finding negates the Keynesian theory. This finding supports Ogbuagu and Ekpenyong (2015). This result shows that if recurrent expenditure is increased by one billion-naira, economic growth will fall by 0.004 percent (*ceteris paribus*). Interestingly, the impact of government integrity on economic growth is positive even in the long run. This suggests that the 12 percent increase in economic growth arising from government integrity could be explained by improved checks and policy implementation by institutions responsible for monitoring government fiscal activities.

Unfortunately, when government integrity is interacted with recurrent expenditures, the long-run impact on economic growth becomes negative, rather than the expected positive effect. This implies that a 1-unit increase in the interactive effect would downplay economic growth by 0.0001. The economic interpretation of this finding connotes that the level of government integrity is not strong enough to complement and stimulate the impact of fiscal policy instruments to drive growth in Nigeria. Besides the interaction, recurrent expenditures, capital expenditures, and government integrity are significant at 5% levels. The error correction term is -0.091, which implies the speed of adjustment of 0.09, and it will take approximately 11 years for the disequilibrium in the model to be cleared.

Table 5: Short-Run ARDL Regression Result

DEP VAR: GDPGR				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
$\Delta(\text{CEX})$	-0.013***	0.005	-2.622	0.015
$\Delta(\text{CON})$	0.009**	0.004	2.214	0.037
$\Delta(\text{EXCH})$	-0.020	0.028	-0.718	0.480
$\Delta(\text{GOINT})$	0.035	0.072	0.476	0.638
$\Delta(\text{INTR})$	0.198***	0.067	2.941	0.007
$\Delta(\text{INV})$	-0.319***	0.085	-3.770	0.001
$\Delta(\text{NEXP})$	0.000	0.000	1.626	0.117
$\Delta(\text{REX})$	-0.002***	0.0024	-0.674	0.000
$\Delta(\text{REX*GOINT})$	-0.0001	0.0001	-0.840	0.409
ECM (-1)	-0.091***	0.138	-7.852	0.000

Source: Authors' computation, 2023 *** and ** represents 1% and 5% levels of significance

4.4 Long Run ARDL Relationship of the Variables

According to Onifade et al. (2020), a steady increase in capital expenditures do not translate into the desired economic performance because of the level of corruption and the mismanagement of public funds by syndicates whose expertise lies in budget padding and racketeering. Arguably, these have distorted efforts directed at achieving transparent budget appropriation and execution of capital projects. Nigeria is still trapped in huge infrastructural deficits, which militate the nation's economic growth trajectory (Alimov, 2022; Sulaeman & Sukmana, 2023). More so, recurrent expenditures not only continue to rise but encompass a higher percentage of public spending. Hitherto, this has not translated into improved economic performance, as explained by the Keynesian theory (Ogbuagu & Ekpenyong, 2015). More importantly, the rising trend in government capital and recurrent expenditures could be largely inflationary in nature (Sharaf, 2021). For instance, Nigerian budgets are dominated in Dollar. Given the rate of Naira depreciation against the US dollar, it is arguable that this arbitrary rise in public spending is only "imaginary".

The interactive effects between recurrent expenditure and government integrity maintained an inverse relationship with economic growth in the short-run and long-run periods. This might be explained by the Nigeria's weak average government integrity index between 1991 and 2021 (Aden, 2022). It can be concluded that recurrent spending and government integrity are substitutable since attempts to improve the budgetary process (budget monitoring and implementation) involve funds that might trade off available fund allocated to boost the recurrent expenditures. Also, the low values of Nigeria's government integrity index explain its negative impact on economic growth when interacted with fiscal policy instruments in the model.

The long-run results depict that the impact of capital expenditure on economic growth is positive. First, the finding is in line with *a priori* expectations. More so, the long-run period provides favourable time-path required for capital

expenditure to influence economic growth to its steady-state. The positive effect of capital expenditure on economic performance is achieved because capital expenditure has high multiplier effects on economic performance (Emmanuel, Usifoh & Adu, 2024). Contrary to the above, recurrent expenditures maintained a negative impact on economic growth. This was accounted for by the continuous decline in real wage rate, arising from inflationary pressures, which are disincentives to economic performance (Nwaka & Onifade, 2015).

Table 6: Long Run ARDL Regression Result

DEP VAR: GDPGR				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CEX	0.0082**	0.0044	1.9637	0.0332
CON	0.0079**	0.0035	2.2817	0.0317
EXCH	-0.0187	0.0259	-0.7218	0.4774
GOVIN	0.1216**	0.0664	2.4750	0.0388
INTR	0.1810***	0.0586	3.0890	0.0050
INV	-0.2919***	0.0644	-4.5287	0.0001
NEXP	0.0000	0.0000	1.6317	0.1158
REX	-0.0041**	0.0022	-1.9768	0.0450
REX*GOINT	-0.0001	0.0001	-0.8360	0.4114
C	9.7542	6.0609	1.6094	0.1206

Note: *** & ** represent 1% and 5% levels of Significance

Source: Authors’ computation, 2023

4.4 Post Diagnostic Test

The study employed heteroscedasticity, serial autocorrelation and functional tests as part of its robustness checks, using the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey and Ramsey RESET tests respectively (Table 7). From the results, the resultant p-values of the F-statistic computed from the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey heteroscedasticity and serial correlation LM tests were 0.1064 and 0.5825 respectively; whereas the Ramsey RESET test is 0.1988. This implies an acceptance of the null hypotheses, which supports the absence of heteroscedasticity and serial correlation problems in the models as presented in Table 7 below.

Table 7: Post-Estimation Result

Tests	F-Stat	DF	Prob. Value
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	1.824416	(13,21)	0.1064
Breusch-Godfrey	0.556104	(2, 19)	0.5825
Ramsey RESET	9.598978	(1, 1)	0.1988

Source: Authors’ computation, 20235.

Conclusions and Policy Formulation

This study employed ARDL technique to investigate the role of government integrity in public spending-economic performance relations in Nigeria, covering a 41-year period. The short-run results revealed a contradiction of the Keynesian theory since capital and recurrent spending exerted a negative impact on GDP growth. The interactive effect of recurrent expenditure and government integrity remained negative in the short- and long-run periods. Interestingly, the long run effect of capital expenditure exerted a positive impact on economic growth, which provides theoretical credence to the Keynesian theory. It is on this premise that the paper concludes that the interaction between government integrity and fiscal spending is substitutable. More efforts should be targeted at increasing capital spending as well as ensuring full implementation of capital projects within a budget year since it triggers multiplier effects on the aggregate economy. Also, concerted efforts should be made toward monitoring and prosecution of corrupt government officials, which will in turn improve the level of government integrity along the budget implementation corridors. Particularly, policies should be geared toward increasing the current capital expenditure thresholds as well as political will in the area of monitoring and ensuring the full implementation of capital projects by all stakeholders.

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